

DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF ADHESIVE SMALL BOWEL OBSTRUCTION WITH USING LAPAROSCOPIC METHOD

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Abstract: Adhesive disease of the abdominal cavity, complicated by acute intestinal obstruction, is one of the most difficult diseases of the abdominal cavity in terms of treatment and diagnosis. The urgency of the problem is determined by the complexity of prevention and treatment of the studied complication, the widespread increase in surgical activity, the expansion of indications for performing operations of extended volume and combined interventions for diseases of the abdominal cavity and retroperitoneal space. Analysis of the literature shows that acute intestinal obstruction occupies one of the first places among urgent pathology of the abdominal cavity in terms of the frequency of complications and fatal outcomes.

An increase in the number of patients, the severity and recurrent nature of the disease, difficulties in diagnosis, unsatisfactory immediate and long-term results of treatment of patients with adhesive small bowel obstruction, as well as a high percentage of disability determines the relevance of the chosen topic.

Keywords: laparoscopy, laparotomy, lysis of adhesions, intestinal obstruction, adhesive disease.

ДИАГНОСТИКА И ЛЕЧЕНИЕ СПАЕЧНОЙ ТОНКОКИШЕЧНОЙ НЕПРОХОДИМОСТИ ЛАПАРОСКОПИЧЕСКИМ МЕТОДОМ

Аннотация: Спаечная болезнь органов брюшной полости, осложненная острой кишечной непроходимостью, является одним из наиболее сложных в лечении и диагностике заболеваний органов брюшной полости. Актуальность проблемы определяется сложностью профилактики и лечения изучаемого осложнения, повсеместным ростом хирургической активности, расширением показаний к выполнению операций расширенного объема и комбинированных вмешательств при заболеваниях органов брюшной полости и забрюшинного пространства. Анализ литературы показывает, что острая кишечная непроходимость занимает одно из первых мест среди неотложной патологии органов брюшной полости по частоте осложнений и летальных исходов.

Увеличение числа больных, тяжесть и рецидивирующий характер заболевания, трудности диагностики, неудовлетворительные ближайшие и отдаленные результаты лечения больных со спаечной тонкокишечной непроходимостью, а также высокий процент инвалидизации определяют актуальность выбранная тема.

Ключевые слова: лапароскопия, лапаротомия, лизис спаек, кишечная непроходимость, спаечная болезнь.

INTRODUCTION

Adhesive small bowel obstruction is the cause of emergency hospitalizations in 10-20% of cases, and in 30% - emergency surgical interventions. It should be noted that among the patients who have had an episode of adhesive small bowel obstruction, only 15 - 21% of patients remain

fully functional during the first year. Relapse rates remain excessively high, reaching 32%, and the level of postoperative mortality varies, according to various data, from 2 to 35%, depending on the severity of the patient's condition, the form and duration of the disease. To date, it has been shown that in a significant number of patients operated on for adhesive small bowel obstruction, single adhesions are detected during laparotomy, but the trauma of access to perform adhesiolysis exceeds the intraabdominal injury caused during the main stage of the operation, which subsequently leads to the development of new adhesions. Thus, a kind of "pathological circle" is formed. Traditional surgical interventions performed for intestinal obstruction, according to some researchers, cause a relapse of adhesive disease in 90% of cases.

Analysis of the literature shows that acute intestinal obstruction occupies one of the first places among urgent pathology of the abdominal cavity in terms of the frequency of complications and fatal outcomes.

Purpose of the research: Optimize the diagnosis and treatment of patients with adhesive small bowel obstruction.

MATERIALS AND METHODS OF THE RESEARCH

The results of diagnostics and treatment of 106 patients admitted to the surgical Department of the Samarkand city medical Association and Republican research center for emergency care with a diagnosis of adhesive small bowel obstruction for the period from 2017 to 2020 were analyzed. The results of surgical treatment of 39 patients with adhesive small bowel obstruction during this period were studied.

Criteria for inclusion of patients in the research:

- 1) Surgical treatment of adhesive small bowel obstruction
- 2) Stable hemodynamic parameters at the time of establishing indications for surgery (I-III degree of ASA).
- 3) Age > 18 years; informed consent.

Exclusion criteria from the research:

- 1) Intestinal obstruction as a complication of cancer of tumor origin.
- 2) The severity of the patient's condition exceeds the risk of surgery.
- 3) Inability to track long-term results of a patient's treatment over the course of a year.

The average age was 42.7 ± 6.4 years (median age was 41.5 years; range from 18 to 65 years). There were 37 males (33%) and 69 females (67%).

To assess the effectiveness of laparoscopic access in cases of adhesive small bowel obstruction, patients were divided into two groups (the main group and the comparison group).

The main group included 30 patients (28%) who underwent laparoscopic adhesiolysis. The comparison group included 76 patients (72%) who underwent adhesiolysis and resolution of adhesive small bowel obstruction using laparotomic access.

The average age of the main group of patients was 29.4 ± 5.7 years (median was 32.6 years; interval from 18 to 61 years). There were 11 males (36.7%) and 19 females (63.3%).

The average age of the control group of patients was 38.5 ± 4.4 years (median was 39.7 years; interval from 18 to 65 years). There were 27 males (35.5%) and 49 females (64.5%).

From the data presented in the table, it can be seen that the most common causes of previous surgical interventions were gynecological diseases, acute appendicitis, acute cholecystitis, and pinched hernias of the anterior abdominal wall.

Table 1
Structure of diseases for which patients were operated before treatment (n=39)

Diseases	Quantity (n)	
	Main group n=11	Control group n=28
Gynecological diseases (polycystic ovaries, chronic inflammatory diseases of the appendages, ovarian apoplexy, uterine fibroids)	4 (36,3%)	9 (32,1%)
Acute appendicitis, including the development of appendicular infiltrate and peritonitis	3 (27,3%)	6 (21,4%)
Acute cholecystitis	2 (18,2%)	3 (10,8%)
Strangulated inguinal hernia/ umbilical hernia	2 (18,2%)	4 (14,2%)
Gastric ulcer, complicated by bleeding and perforation	-	2 (7,1%)
Diverticular disease of the colon	-	1 (3,6%)
Closed trauma/ penetrating stab wounds to the abdomen	-	3 (10,8%)

It is noteworthy that in the first 6 hours from the onset of the disease, 4 (10.2%) patients were admitted to the emergency Department, from 6 to 12 hours — 12 (30.8%), from 12 to 24 hours — 14 (35.8%) cases; after a day or more, 9 (23.2%) patients were admitted.

Generally accepted physical examination methods were used during the examination. The main complaints in the presence of adhesive small bowel obstruction were: pain and bloating, delayed discharge of gases and stool. Patients also complained of dry mouth, nausea, vomiting, weakness, which is associated with water-electrolyte disorders.

Diagnostics of adhesive small bowel obstruction included clinical and laboratory examination, ultrasound examination (ultrasound), x-ray examination of the abdominal cavity (including using radiopaque drugs followed by dynamic polyposition enterography), intestinal scintigraphy, abdominal MSCT.

After surgical intervention, the duration of the operation, the duration of postoperative hospital stay, and postoperative complications that occurred within 30 days after surgical treatment were evaluated. In addition, long-term results were evaluated: relapse of the disease, repeated hospitalizations.

THE RESULTS OF THE RESEARCH AND THEIR DISCUSSION

Out of 106 patients admitted to the surgical Department of the Samarkand city medical Association and Republican research center for emergency care in the period 2012-2017, 7 patients (6.6%) were identified as having indications for emergency surgery at the level of the emergency Department:

1. Suspicion of strangulation acute intestinal obstruction - 4 patients (with impaired or questionable intestinal viability-1)
2. Clinical picture of peritonitis - 1 patients (cause-necrosis of the small intestine with subsequent perforation of the organ)
3. "Started" acute intestinal obstruction with a sharp expansion of the loops of the small intestine to 5-6 cm in diameter - 2 patients (risk of intestinal rupture).

Diagnostic laparoscopy was performed in one patient with a clinical picture of strangulation obstruction. Laparoscopic adhesiolysis with a dissection of the rod was performed.

There was no violation of the viability of the intestinal wall, there was no conversion.

Table 2

Indications for emergency surgery at the emergency Department level

Views	Main group n=1	Control group n=6
Strangulation obstruction	1	3
Peritonitis	-	1
The threat of rupture of the intestine	-	2

Laparotomy was performed in 6 patients for emergency indications.

In the absence of indications for emergency surgery, conservative treatment was initiated in 99 cases (93.4%), including infusion, antispasmodic therapy, siphon enemas, nasogastric drainage, and courses of hyperbaric oxygenation. If conservative treatment is ineffective, indications for surgery were established in 31 (31.3%) patients.

(22.6%) patients were operated with laparoscopic access for emergency-delayed indications. Conversion was required in 4 cases (36.4%). Indications for access conversion during emergency delayed laparoscopy were:

1. Widespread diffuse peritonitis (1);
2. Necrosis or doubts about the viability of the intestine (1);
3. Adhesive process in the abdominal cavity of the III - IV degree according to the classification of Blinnikov O. I. (2), which led in 1 case to intestinal perforation during the formation of pneumoperitoneum.

Table 3

Distribution of patients in the compared groups depending on the access of surgical intervention and the prevalence of adhesions in the abdominal cavity n=39

Severity of the adhesive process (degree) according to the classification of O. I. Blinnikov	Main group, n = 11		Control group, n =28		Total
	Planning and delayed lysis of adhesions n =3	Emergency adhesions n =8	Lysis of adhesions after ineffective conservative treatment, n =23	Emergency adhesions n =5	
I	2	2	6	-	10 (25,6%)
II	1	5	7	2	15 (38,5%)
III	-	1	6	3	10 (25,6%)
IV	-	-	4	-	4 (10,3%)

Successful conservative treatment was observed in 68 patients (68,7%).

Laparoscopic adhesiolysis after resolution of adhesive small bowel obstruction was performed in 3 (7.7% of all operated patients) cases, taking into account its recurrent course and previous "small laparotomies" and laparoscopic interventions (appendectomy, gynecological interventions) in the anamnesis.

Thus, after analyzing the data of retrospective and prospective studies, we found that laparoscopic access is most effective and safe in patients who were admitted early from the onset of the disease with a clinical picture of strangulation, after a history of small laparotomies. The

adhesive process of the 4th degree according to the classification of Blinnikov O. I. is dangerous with iatrogenic injuries. Laparoscopic interventions after ineffective conservative treatment have worse results, which is associated with a large diameter of intestinal loops with long-term obstruction and lack of working space in the abdominal cavity.

In the course of working out the technique of laparoscopic surgery, we established the following sequence of intervention stages: in case of detection of an ocoustic window, according to ultrasound of the abdominal cavity, the pneumoperitoneum was applied as standard using a Veresh needle or —open” by the Hasson method in its absence. Based on the laparoscopic revision data, the possibility of performing laparoscopic adhesiolysis was finally evaluated in accordance with the classification proposed by O. I. Blinnikov (1988). During laparoscopic revision of the abdominal cavity, first of all, the location of the collapsed intestinal loops was determined. The examination was performed retrograde: from the ileocecal transition to the Treitz ligament. The intersection of the adhesions that caused intestinal obstruction was performed acutely, without the use of coagulation. If the adhesion process was common, then only one "causal" junction was crossed. When coagulation was necessary, dielectric shears or ultrasonic shears were mainly used. If the intestinal wall is damaged, it may be sutured with separate nodular sutures on nontraumatic needle. After removing the obstruction, a 0.5% solution of novocaine (50 to 80 ml) was injected into the mesentery root to prevent gastrointestinal paresis in the early postoperative period.

In the presence of stretched loops of the small intestine more than 4 cm, intraoperative nasointestinal intubation was performed using intestinoscopy in 1 (1.4%) cases. The operation was completed by draining the abdominal cavity. Installed silicone drainage in the pelvic cavity through contraportada in the right iliac region.

Postoperative complications that developed in the main group of patients included: persistent postoperative intestinal paresis in one case (1.4%), which was resolved conservatively, but required the use of parenteral nutrition.

The duration of postoperative hospital stay with traditional laparotomic access ranged from 8 to 19 days (average 13 ± 4.5 days), with laparoscopic access from 5 to 9 days (median 6.4 days) ($p < 0.05$). Taking into account the results obtained and the data from the preoperative examination, we can conclude that laparoscopic intervention, in addition to minimizing the trauma of the operation, requires strict selection of patients to reduce the risk of both intraoperative and early postoperative complications.

There is a risk of performing laparoscopic adhesiolysis at the height of intestinal obstruction, especially in the presence of infiltrate, which may require conversion in some

cases to minimize the risks of intraoperative complications of laparotomic access. However, in compliance with all principles of urgent laparoscopic surgery, including high levels of expertise of the operating team, having extensive experience in both routine and emergency laparoscopic operations, in the absence of exceeding the indications for minimally invasive surgery treatment outcome of this group of patients will be positive, which was confirmed by the data of medical documentation and results of questionnaire in the remote terms after the operation.

CONCLUSIONS

1. In 6.6% of patients admitted with adhesive small bowel obstruction, the indication for emergency surgery at the level of the emergency Department was strangulation acute intestinal obstruction, common peritonitis. In 93.4%, conservative treatment is indicated, which is effective in 68.7%, and in 31.3% of cases, emergency surgical treatment is indicated.

After resolving adhesive small bowel obstruction on the background of conservative treatment, the indication for planned delayed surgery from laparotomy access is a recurrent course of adhesive disease (from 2 to 4 times a year) and a history of "small operations".

2. The use of laparoscopic access reduced the number of postoperative complications to 5.4%, versus 15.8% after laparotomy, and the duration of hospitalization to 5 ± 1.4 days, versus 13 ± 4.5 , respectively.

3. The modern therapeutic and diagnostic algorithm should include diagnostic and therapeutic laparoscopy, which can be used for emergency surgical interventions in 6.6% of cases, after ineffective conservative treatment in 22.6%, and planned-delayed in 100% of cases with recurrent course of adhesive small bowel obstruction after a positive effect of the therapy.

In 22.6% of cases, laparoscopic access can be used and its use is most justified in a planned and delayed manner after conservative resolution of intestinal obstruction.

REFERENCES:

1. Abdullaev S. et al. Problems of Diagnostics, Prevention and Surgical Tactics of Treatment of Adhesive-Intestinal Obstruction //Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology. – 2021. – C. 2289-2294.
2. Abdurakhmanovich A. A., Furkatovich A. R. Methods of early surgical treatment of Burns //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 6. – C. 528-532.
3. Akhmedov S. K. et al. Значение раннего энтерального питания у больных с синдромом интраабдоминальной гипертензии при тяжелом остром панкреатите //Инновационное развитие: потенциал науки и современного образования. – 2020. – C. 274-276.
4. Alisherovich U. K. et al. EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MULTI-STAGE SURGICAL TACTICS IN SEVERE LIVER DAMAGE //Research Focus. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 1. – C. 312-318.
5. Alisherovich U. K., Rashidovich S. H., Ugli K. Y. E. OUR EXPERIENCE IN CONSERVATIVE TREATMENT OF SPLEEN INJURY IN CLOSED ABDOMINAL TRAUMA //Research Focus. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 1. – C. 319-325.
6. Elmuradov G. O. K. et al. QORIN BO ‘SHLIG ‘I YOPIQ JAROHATLARIDA SONOGRAFIYA VA VIDEOELAPAROSKOPIYANI QO’LLASH //Research Focus. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 1. – C. 173-180.
7. Elmuradov G. O. K. et al. QORIN BO ‘SHLIG ‘I YOPIQ JAROHATLARIDA SONOGRAFIYA VA VIDEOELAPAROSKOPIYANI QO’LLASH //Research Focus. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 1. – C. 173-180.
8. Erkinovich K. Y. Methods of early surgical treatment of burns //Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS). – 2022. – T. 2. – №. Special Issue 4. – C. 184-188.
9. Kamoliddin K., Muxammad A., Nilufar H. RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNI INSON HAYOTIDAGI O’RNI //Research Focus. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 1. – C. 594-600.
10. Khursanov Y. E. Amniotic membrane as an effective biological wound covering //UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL № CI-1. – 2021. – C. 30-36.
11. Shonazarov I. et al. Analysis of the results of surgical tactics and treatment in patients with acute necrotic pancreatitis //European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine. – 2020. – T. 7. – №. 3. – C. 3130-3135.

12. Shonazarov I. et al. Diagnosis and treatment of adhesive small bowel obstruction with using laparoscopic method //European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine. – 2020. – Т. 7. – №. 3. – С. 3192-3198.
13. Temirovich A. M. et al. CRF AND CKD: MODERN APPROACHES TO TERMINOLOGY, CLASSIFICATION, DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT //Research Focus. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 79-90.
14. Temirovich A. M. et al. Prevention and treatment of intraabdominal hypertension in patients with peritonitis //Вестник науки и образования. – 2021. – №. 3-2 (106). – С. 75-79.
15. Voxid F., Xolbek X., Kamoliddin X. Sorting the object based on neural networks computer vision algorithm of the system and software //ijtimoiy fanlarda innovasiya onlayn ilmiy jurnali. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 67-69.
16. Абдуллаев С. А. и др. КЛАССИФИКАЦИЯ СОЧЕТАННОЙ ТРАВМЫ ГРУДИ И ЖИВОТА //Скорая медицинская помощь. – 2003. – Т. 4. – №. 4. – С. 18-18.
17. Абдуллаев С. А. и др. ПРОГНОЗИРОВАНИЕ ТЯЖЕСТИ ТРАВМЫ И ИСХОДА ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ПОСТРАДАВШИХ С СОЧЕТАННОЙ ТРАВМОЙ ГРУДИ И ЖИВОТА //Скорая медицинская помощь. – 2003. – Т. 4. – №. 4. – С. 19-20.
18. АВАЗОВ А. А. и др. KUYISHLARDA ERTA XIRURGIK DAVOLASH USULLARI //ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ. – 2022. – Т. 7. – №. 4.
19. Авазов А. А., Хурсанов Ё. Э. ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ ЛЕЧЕБНО-ДИАГНОСТИЧЕСКИХ МЕТОДОВ НЕКРОЭКТОМИИ У БОЛЬНЫХ С РАННИМИ ОЖОГАМИ //Journal the Coryphaeus of Science. – 2023. – Т. 5. – №. 2. – С. 19-22.
20. Авазов А. А., Хурсанов Ё. Э. У., Мухаммадиев М. Х. ВОЗМОЖНОСТЬ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ИНТЕГРАЛЬНОЙ ШКАЛЫ BISAP ДЛЯ ПРОГНОЗИРОВАНИЯ РАЗВИТИЯ ТЯЖЕЛОГО ОСТРОГО ПАНКРЕАТИТА //Research Focus. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 158-164.
21. Авазов А. А., Хурсанов Ё. Э. У., Шакиров Б. М. ҚЎЛНИНГ ЧУҚУР КУЙИШИНИ ДАВОЛАШ ТАКТИКАСИ //Research Focus. – 2022. – №. Special issue 1. – С. 35-42.
22. Авазов А. А., Хурсанов Ё. Э. У., Шакиров Б. М. ҚЎЛНИНГ ЧУҚУР КУЙИШИНИ ДАВОЛАШ ТАКТИКАСИ //Research Focus. – 2022. – №. Special issue 1. – С. 35-42.
23. Ахмедов Р. Ф. и др. Диагностическая значимость уровня прокальцитонина при ожоговой болезни //Журнал Неотложная хирургия им. ИИ Джанелидзе. – 2021. – №. S1. – С. 11-12.
24. Ахмедов Р. Ф. и др. Наш опыт лечения ожогового сепсиса //Журнал Неотложная хирургия им. ИИ Джанелидзе. – 2021. – №. S1. – С. 10-11.
25. Ачилов М. Т. и др. Диагностика и хирургическая коррекция синдрома Мириizzi //Re-health journal. – 2020. – №. 2-2 (6). – С. 111-113.
26. Ачилов М. Т. и др. Диагностические особенности и методы хирургической тактики билиарного илеуса //журнал биомедицины и практики. – 2021. – Т. 6. – №. 1.
27. Ачилов М. Т. и др. ОЦЕНКА ЛЕЧЕБНОГО ПОЛИХИМИОТЕРАПИИ ПРИ РАКЕ МОЛОЧНОЙ ЖЕЛЕЗЫ //Research Focus. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 62-69.
28. Ачилов М. Т. и др. Панкреатодуоденальная резекция-методика физиологической реконструкции //Достижения науки и образования. – 2020. – №. 6 (60). – С. 38-42.
29. Ачилов М. Т. и др. Ручной колоанальный или аппаратный колоректальный анастомоз //Достижения науки и образования. – 2020. – №. 6 (60). – С. 43-44.

30. Даминов Ф. А., Карабаев Х. К., Хурсанов Ё. Э. ПРИНЦИПЫ МЕСТНОГО ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ОЖОГОВЫХ РАН У ТЯЖЕЛООБОЖЖЕННЫХ (Обзор литературы) //Research Focus. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 3. – С. 133-142.
31. Даминов Ф. А., Хурсанов Ё. Э., Карабаев Х. К. НАШ ОПЫТ ПРОФИЛАКТИКИ И ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ПОЛИОРГАННОЙ НЕДОСТАТОЧНОСТИ У ТЯЖЕЛООБОЖЖЕННЫХ //Research Focus. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 3. – С. 143-151.
32. Джаббаров Ш. Р., Хурсанов Ё. Э. У. STANDARDIZATION OF THE THERAPEUTIC DIAGNOSTIC APPROACH FOR COMBINED CLOSED INTESTINAL INJURY //Research Focus. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 3. – С. 120-132.
33. Джаббаров Ш. Р., Хурсанов Ё. Э. У. ПОСЛЕОПЕРАЦИОННОЙ ЛЕТАЛЬНОСТИ ПРИ ОСТРОМ ХОЛЕЦИСТИТЕ //Research Focus. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 3. – С. 152-161.
34. Камолидинов С. А. и др. Лапароскопическая диагностика и лечение спаечной кишечной непроходимости //World science: problems and innovations. – 2020. – С. 270-275.
35. Курбонов Н. А., Ахмедов Р. Ф. Modern approaches to the treatment of deep burning patients //узбекский медицинский журнал. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 2.
36. Мустафакулов И. Б., Карабаев Х. К., Джураева З. А. Amniotic membrane-as an effective biological wound covering //узбекский медицинский журнал. – 2021. – №. Special 1.
37. Мустафакулов И. Б., Умедов Х. А. Surgical tactics in case of isolated injuries of small and large intestine //узбекский медицинский журнал. – 2022. – т. 3. – №. 2.
38. Облакулов З. Т. и др. Видеолапароскопическое лечение острой спаечной кишечной непроходимости //Достижения науки и образования. – 2020. – №. 1 (55). – С. 70-73.
39. Рузибоев С. А., Авазов А. А., Хурсанов Е. Э. СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЕ РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ПОСЛЕОПЕРАЦИОННЫХ И РЕЦИДИВНЫХ ГРЫЖ ПЕРЕДНЕЙ БРЮШНОЙ СТЕНКИ //Research Focus. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 184-191.
40. Рузиев П. Н. и др. Опыт консервативного лечения повреждения селезенки при закрытой травме живота //Скорая медицинская помощь-2022. – 2022. – С. 109-110.
41. Рузиев П. Н. и др. Результаты лечения тромбоза мезентериальных сосудов //Роль больниц скорой помощи и научно исследовательских институтов в снижении предотвратимой смертности среди населения. – 2018. – С. 190-191.
42. Саттаров Ш. Х., Рузибаев С. А., Хурсанов Ё. Э. ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ ПУТИ КОРРЕКЦИИ ЭНДОТОКСИКОЗА ПРИ ОСТРОМ ПЕРИТОНИТЕ (ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ) //Research Focus. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 144-150.
43. Саттаров Ш. Х., Рузибаев С. А., Хурсанов Ё. Э. РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ОСТРОГО РАЗЛИТОГО ГНОЙНОГО ПЕРИТОНИТА С ПРИМЕНЕНИЕМ ЛАПАРОСТОМИИ //Research Focus. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 238-242.
44. Тухтаев Б. Х. и др. Тактика лечения пищеводно-желудочных кровотечений у больных с синдромом портальной гипертензии //Достижения науки и образования. – 2020. – №. 1 (55). – С. 79-82.
45. Тухтаев Ж. К., Хурсанов Ё. Э. У. ДИФфузНЫЙ ТОКСИЧЕСКИЙ ЗОБ ЦИТОВИДНОЙ ЖЕЛЕЗЫ //Research Focus. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 20-31.
46. Хамроев Г. А., Хурсанов Ё. Э. ОРГАНОСОХРАНЯЮЩАЯ ОПЕРАЦИЯ ПРИ МАССИВНОМ РАЗМОЗЖЕНИИ ЯИЧКА //Research Focus. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 3. – С. 185-194.

47. Хурсанов Ё. Э. У., Жуманов Х. А. У., Эргашев А. Ф. СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ МЕТОДОВ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ БОЛЬНЫХ С ТЯЖЕЛЫМИ ОЖОГАМИ //Research Focus. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 332-340.
48. ХУРСАНОВ Я. Э. и др. ТАКТИКА ХИРУРГИЧЕСКОГО ЛЕЧЕНИЯ БОЛЬНЫХ С ГЛУБОКИМИ ОЖОГАМИ //ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ. – 2022. – Т. 7. – №. 5.
49. Шакиров Б., Авазов А., Хурсанов Ё. COMPREHENSIVE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH EXTENSIVE DEEP BURNS LOWER LIMBS //EurasianUnionScientists. – 2022. – С. 24-26.
50. Шоназаров И. и др. Наш опыт диагностики и лечения повреждений двенадцатиперстной кишки при сочетанной абдоминальной травме //Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины. – 2017. – №. 3 (96). – С. 122-125.
51. ШОНАЗАРОВ И. Ш. и др. Ўт тош касаллиги сабабли ўтказилган операциядан кейинги сафроли перитонитни даволашда миниинвазив усулларнинг клиник самарадорлиги //журнал биомедицины и практики. – 2022. – Т. 7. – №. 6.
52. ШОНАЗАРОВ И. Ш. и др. Холецистэктомиядан кейинги асоратларни коррекциясида диапевтик ва рентгенэндобилиар аралашувларни қўллаш //журнал биомедицины и практики. – 2022. – Т. 7. – №. 6.
53. Шоназаров И. Ш. и др. ЧРЕСДРЕНАЖНАЯ САНАЦИЯ БИЛИАРНОГО ТРАКТА В ПРОФИЛАКТИКЕ И ЛЕЧЕНИИ ХОЛАНГИОГЕННЫХ АБЦЕСОВ ПЕЧЕНИ //Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities. – 2023. – Т. 11. – №. 1. – С. 807-816.
54. Шоназаров И. Ш. и др. ЭТАПНОЕ ЛЕЧЕНИЕ ОСТРОГО ХОЛАНГИТА С ПРЕДВАРИТЕЛЬНОЙ ДЕКОМПРЕССИЕЙ ЖЕЛЧНЫХ ПРОТОКОВ //Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities. – 2023. – Т. 11. – №. 1. – С. 817-824.
55. Шоназаров И. Ш. Пути оптимизации диагностики, лечения и прогноза острой спаечной тонкокишечной непроходимости : дис. – Ташкент, 2008.
56. Шоназаров И. Ш., Мизамов Ф. О., Хурсанов Ё. Э. ДИАПЕВТИЧЕСКИЕ И РЕНТГЕНЭНДОБИЛИАРНЫЕ ВМЕЩАТЕЛЬСТВА В КОРРЕКЦИИ ОСЛОЖНЕНИЙ ПОСЛЕ ХОЛЕЦИСТЭКТОМИИ //Research Focus. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 44-51.
57. Шоназаров И. Ш., Мизамов Ф. О., Хурсанов Ё. Э. ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ПРИОРИТЕТНОГО ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ МИНИИНВАЗИВНЫХ ВМЕЩАТЕЛЬСТВ В ХИРУРГИЧЕСКОМ ЛЕЧЕНИИ ОСЛОЖНЕННЫХ ФОРМ ОСТРОГО ХОЛЕЦИСТИТА //Research Focus. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 36-43.
58. Элмурадов Г. К., Шукуров Б. И. ВИДЕОЭНДОХИРУРГИЯ В ДИАГНОСТИКЕ И ЛЕЧЕНИИ РАЗРЫВОВ ДИАФРАГМЫ //THEORY AND ANALYTICAL ASPECTS OF RECENT RESEARCH. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 7. – С. 40-58.
59. Эльмурадов А., Хурсанов Ё. Э. У. ПОСТКОЛОНИАЛЬНАЯ/ДЕКОЛОНИАЛЬНАЯ КРИТИКА И ТЕОРИЯ МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ ОТНОШЕНИЙ //Research Focus. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 198-208.
60. Юлдашев Ш. С. и др. Болада ёт жисм таъсирида қизилунгач перфорациям //Вестник экстренной медицины. – 2016. – №. 4. – С. 69-71.